

Arctic connectivity meets autonomy and sustainability

A tale from the North

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Copper network

Copper networks are currently being phased out in many parts of the country. Instead, broadband services and subscriptions are offered via fibre and mobile networks.

- Industry
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PTS > Private > Internet > Copper network

3G networks will be switched off by 31 December 2024

2G networks will be switched off by 31 December 2025

What about connectivity in rural and remote places ?

27 March 2023

with 2G/3G

without 2G/3G

27 March 2023

with 2G/3G

without 2G/3G

Contents

- I. Will 6G bridge the urban-rural divide?
- II. Measuring the divide
- III. Ideas & initiatives in Sweden
- IV. What to expect?

The urban

The rural

I. Reasons why 6G will *not* bridge the urban-rural divide

1. The first five generations did not

2. The targets are moving

Swedish government – Broadband Strategy, set in 2016:

by 2025:

98% access to at least 1 Gbit/s (2% = 90000 households)

99.9% access to at least 100 Mbit/s (0.1% = 4500 households)

100% access to at least 30 Mbit/s

and:

mobile coverage “wherever people reside and move”

Urbanization is a solution? But Sweden now has *Ruralisation*

3. Every problem looks like a nail

Technology is not the problem !

I. Reasons why the urban-rural divide may actually be bridged

1. New emerging societal values

- Public services
- Health sector
- Safety / security / Resilience
- Attractive regions

2. New emerging economic values

- Agriculture/forestry
- Mining
- Tourism
- Transport/logistics
- Maritime sector

3. Democratic values

- Hope
- Participation
- Inclusion

4. Rapid developments in space

Market segment

The unconnected are more likely to be:

Poorer

Rural

Less educated

Older

Women

Market segment characterisation

Rural areas with low levels of existing **infrastructure** and **connectivity** solutions

Rural areas with limited access to on-grid **electricity**

Low levels of **purchasing power** in the general population

Lack of access to other **traditional services**, such as banking of MFS

Existing business models reinforce these correlations

II. Measurement and data analytics

Understanding and measuring the urban-rural divide

Measuring the cellular coverage

Norrboten County

Norrbotten County

Norrbotten County

Norrbottnen County

Sudheesh, van de Beek,
"Mobile Coverage in Rural Sweden: Analysis of a
Comparative Measurement Campaign",
Mobile Information Systems, Article ID 8869534.

New measures of inequality

2019

Cellular coverage

Population

Cellular Coverage Inequality

“inequality”

“equality”

Further questions:

- Can we predict the coverage development?
- Can we train an ML model to generalize to new regions and markets ?
- Can a regulator use this information ?

III. Ideas & initiatives in the north of Sweden

#FULLTÄCKNING

RURAL ICT TEST BED

Laevas sameby

netmore

1980s

1st generation mobile networks, in Sweden: NMT450 (analogue cellular) and PMR
Low frequencies, outdoor coverage everywhere

1990s - today

GSM, 3G, 4G

Higher frequencies, no full coverage anymore

Focus on cities, roads, and railways

... going forward

- local, urban and global coverage
- heterogeneous network owners
- heterogeneous access technologies

umbrella-network

- mobile connectivity everywhere
- backhaul for rural hotspot
- low-frequencies

National operators:

- locally high speed
- new (local) operators
- fiber or umbrella-cell backhaul

Rural Hotspots:

- locally high speed
- new (local) operators
- fiber or umbrella-cell backhaul

Local networks

- Indoor coverage
- Companies and real-estate owners
- guaranteed indoor coverage

Basestations vs. Cell Radius

Open questions

How far we can reach ?

What are the main limitations and possible solutions?

What are the deployment challenges?

Component 1: Ultra-large cells

Swedish Broadcaster TeraCom
is building a 5G-ready network:

- AGA (Air-to-Ground-to-Air) network
- Existing high-mast infrastructure
- Band 40 (2.3 GHz) spectrum assets
- Provide aerial coverage for critical communications
- Across 96% of Sweden's surface area

Teracom and Ericsson

Innovation for agile and high-capacity mobile connectivity

HOME > CASES > HIGH TOWER, HIGH POWER

High tower, high power

Teracom and Ericsson jointly demonstrated usage of Teracom's infrastructure of high masts to connect a deployable network for mission-critical communications, supporting critical services in remote areas for government, public safety and utility companies.

CASE | [5G](#) [5G RAN](#) [Mission Critical Communications](#) [#PPDR](#) [#publicsafety](#)

[#SWAF](#) [#FMV](#) [#5GBusiness](#)

Ludvika, Sweden

Spring 2021

- Umbrella network
- Cell radius up to 80 km
- Rural coverage
- Backhauling: to hotspots

Who wants to buy these base stations?

Bridging the Digital Divide Using SuperCell Massive MIMO

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Hindawi
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WILEY

Research Article

The Potential of Massive-MIMO on TV Towers for Cellular Coverage Extension

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Because of low potential revenue, network operators have mainly focused on providing connectivity in urban areas rather than in rural areas resulting in technology improvement in favour of urban areas; and consequently, most of remote areas suffer from poor or lack of connectivity. In this paper, we present the potential of massive-MIMO to provide connectivity to sparse areas. We show that we can cover large rural areas with radius of tens of km using massive-MIMO mounted on existing infrastructure of TV towers. We also show that, in contrast with common belief, higher frequencies, e.g., 3500 MHz rather than 700 MHz, can reach farther utilizing massive-MIMO, provided that the antenna area is the same.

input multiple output (MIMO) technology for supporting fifth generation communication systems. Due to the traffic in urban areas and to meet

smart agriculture, e-health, and climate monitoring helping the people to progress on education, health, and business levels [3], [4]. In the survey paper [4], it was pointed out that there is no single optimal solution that can provide ubiquitous

Component 2:

Autonomous
rural hotspots

- No roads
- No electricity grid
- No fiber

Coverage

- The highest mobile network in Sweden
- So far it covers about 50km of the "King's trail", a popular hiking trail
- Expansion planned to the South
- Currently in test operation. Commercial operation planned from spring 2023
- 300-400 professional users in the area
- Over 25 000 annual visitors spending an average 1 week in the area
- Important for safety and daily communication needs

- Robust and autonomous radio sites with advanced antennas at strategic locations for max coverage
- Minimum impact fixing of the sites to the bedrock
- Power is supplied 24/7 by a combination of solar, fuel cell and wind
- Pico base stations
- Currently 4G and 2G
- Adapted for Mobile Network Operators, Public Safety and others in need of coverage or rural sites
- Access to the network offered through Roaming or own Network code

Many questions!

- Who plans the radio network and how to access frequency spectrum
- Technical generation – 2G? 5G?
- Power supply and transmission
- Who connects it – and to what?
- Where to connect a local radio network and who makes it happen?
- Who delivers, installs and maintains the network?
- Who ensures there are services that can be used in the local network?
- Who does the marketing to those that need to access the network for coverage?
- etc.

Component 3: Societal towers

Public sector installs tower
NMOs install equipment
NMOs provide services

Is this a sufficiently good offer
for deployment?

Are there sufficiently many
new customers?

STARLINK

RESIDENTIAL

BUSINESS

RV

MARITIME

AVIATION

IOT

AVAILABILITY

AVAILABLE

WAITLIST

COMING SOON

Component 4: LEO satellite constellations

European 5G Observatory

SUPPORTED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
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IN : EU DIGITAL DECADE

NEWS IN THE EU, NEWS OUTSIDE OF THE EU

TAGS: [#5G TRIAL](#), [#NON-TERRESTRIAL 5G](#)

Ericsson, Qualcomm and Thales partner to bring 5G to space

The three companies say they will conduct tests involving non-terrestrial 5G networks connected to smartphones.

Categories

- [5G Action Plan](#)
- [5G auctions](#)
- [5G commercial launch](#)
- [5G pre-commercial launch](#)
- [5G Security Toolbox](#)

- Societal towers
 - Initiative/investment from municipalities and regions
- High towers
 - Technology available !
 - Open for all ?

- Autonomous hotspots
 - Who will build and operate ?
 - Roaming ?
- Space
 - Will happen! And sooner than we think
 - But what what price, sustainably ?

What to expect ?